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ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
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Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
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ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ВЫБОР МЕТОДА УШИВАНИЯ МАТКИ ПРИ КЕСАРЕВОМ СЕЧЕНИИ: АНАЛИЗ АНАМНЕСТИЧЕСКИХ ДАННЫХ.....	76
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ЖУРНАЛ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ И УРО-НЕФРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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Valiev Shukhrat

PhD, Assistant

Samarkand State Medical University

Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Negmadjanov Bakhodur Boltayevich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of Department

Samarkand State Medical University

Samarkand, Uzbekistan

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CHOICE OF UTERINE SUTURING METHOD DURING CESAREAN SECTION: ANALYSIS OF ANAMNESTIC DATA

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ABSTRACT

The choice of the uterine suturing method after a cesarean section plays an important role in reducing the risk of complications and affects subsequent reproductive outcomes. A study was conducted on 496 women aged 18 to 42 years who underwent cesarean section. Patients were divided into two groups depending on the method of uterine suturing: Group 1 – 240 (48%) women with modified uterine suturing, and Group 2 – 256 (52%) women with traditional suturing. The analysis of anamnestic data included the assessment of indications for the first cesarean section, extragenital and gynecological morbidity, as well as previously performed surgical interventions. The obtained results showed that the choice of the uterine suturing method is largely determined by the somatic and obstetric-gynecological history of the patient, requiring an individualized approach to surgical tactics.

Keywords: cesarean section; uterine suturing; obstetric history; gynecological pathology; extragenital morbidity.

Valiev Shukhrat

PhD, Assistant

Samarqand Davlat Tibbiyot Universiteti

Samarqand, O'zbekiston

Negmadjanov Baxodur Boltayevich

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Kafedra mudiri

Samarqand Davlat Tibbiyot Universiteti

Samarqand, O'zbekiston

KESAR KESISH AMALIYOTIDA BACHADONNI TIKISH USULINI TANLASHGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR: ANAMNESTIK MA'LUMOTLARNI TAHLIL QILISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Kesarcha kesish operatsiyasidan keyin bachadonni tikish usulini tanlash asoratlar xavfini kamaytirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi va keyingi reproduktiv natijalarga ta'sir qiladi. 18 dan 42 yoshgacha bo'lgan 496 nafar ayol ishtirokida tadqiqot o'tkazildi. Bemorlar bachadonni tikish usuliga qarab ikki guruhga bo'lindi: 1-guruh – 240 (48%) nafar ayollar bachadonning modifikatsiyalangan tikish usuli bilan, 2-guruh – 256 (52%) nafar ayollar an'anaviy tikish usuli bilan. Anamnestic ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilishda birinchi kesarcha kesish operatsiyasiga ko'rsatmalar, ekstragenital va ginekologik kasalliklar, shuningdek, ilgari o'tkazilgan jarrohlik aralashuvlari baholandi. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, bachadonni tikish usulini tanlash ko'p jihatdan bemorning somatik va akusherlik-ginekologik anamneziga bog'liq bo'lib, individual yondashuvni talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kesarcha kesish; bachadonni tikish; akusherlik anamnezi; ginekologik patologiya; ekstragenital kasalliklar.

Шухрат Валиев

PhD, Ассистент

Самаркандский Государственный медицинский университет

Самарканд, Узбекистан

Негмаджанов Баходур Болтаевич

д.м.н., проф. Заведующий кафедрой
Самаркандский Государственный медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ВЫБОР МЕТОДА УШИВАНИЯ МАТКИ ПРИ КЕСАРЕВОМ СЕЧЕНИИ: АНАЛИЗ АНАМНЕСТИЧЕСКИХ ДАННЫХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Выбор метода ушивания матки после кесарева сечения играет важную роль в снижении риска осложнений и влияет на дальнейшие репродуктивные исходы. Проведено обследование 496 женщин в возрасте от 18 до 42 лет, перенесших кесарево сечение. Пациентки были разделены на две группы в зависимости от метода ушивания матки: 1 группа – 240 (48%) женщин с модифицированным ушиванием матки, 2 группа – 256 (52%) женщин с традиционным ушиванием. Анализ анамнестических данных включал оценку показаний к первому кесаревому сечению, экстрагенитальной и гинекологической заболеваемости, а также ранее перенесенных хирургических вмешательств. Полученные результаты показали, что выбор метода ушивания матки во многом определяется соматическим и акушерско-гинекологическим анамнезом пациентки, что требует индивидуального подхода к хирургической тактике.

Ключевые слова: кесарево сечение; ушивание матки; акушерский анамнез; гинекологическая патология; экстрагенитальная заболеваемость.

The global rate of cesarean sections (CS) continues to rise, reaching 30–40% of all births in some countries [1]. In certain regions, this figure exceeds 50%, underscoring the need to further refine surgical techniques and methods for tissue repair post-surgery [2]. Although cesarean section offers clear benefits when vaginal delivery poses risks to the mother or fetus, it also carries specific challenges related to scar healing, potential complications in subsequent pregnancies, and disruptions to reproductive health [3].

One of the central considerations in postoperative patient management is the choice of uterine closure method. Currently, single- and double-layer sutures are the most common approaches to closing the uterine incision. Research shows that the suturing technique can substantially influence scar quality and integrity, which is particularly critical for women planning future pregnancies [4].

Single-layer uterine closure is associated with several advantages, including a shorter operative time, reduced blood loss, and a decreased likelihood of forming coarse scar tissue. Nevertheless, multiple clinical observations and meta-analyses have shown that a single-layer suture—especially one that includes the decidual layer—may thin the lower uterine segment and elevate the long-term risk of uterine scar dehiscence [5]. Ultrasound studies report that the average myometrial thickness at the scar site with single-layer closure is 3.8–4.6 mm, whereas double-layer closure yields 5.8–6.1 mm [6]. Moreover, the incidence of scar defects (isthmocele) is significantly higher in women who undergo single-layer closure than in those treated with double-layer methods, potentially leading to menstrual irregularities, pelvic pain, and secondary infertility [7].

In contrast, double-layer closure provides a more secure approximation of wound edges, reduces the likelihood of defect formation at the scar site, and fosters a stronger myometrium. Studies have indicated that applying a double-layer closure without fixing the first layer lowers the risk of uterine rupture in subsequent pregnancies by a factor of two to four compared to single-layer closure [8]. This is particularly relevant for women who wish to attempt a vaginal birth after cesarean (VBAC), since scar integrity is a crucial factor in determining the safety of vaginal delivery [9].

The formation of an isthmocele following cesarean section remains a pressing concern in modern obstetric surgery. This defect, which manifests as a thinning or invagination in the area of the uterine scar, occurs in 19–69% of women, depending on the suturing technique used [10]. Women with isthmocele are more prone to dyspareunia, chronic pelvic pain, and intermenstrual bleeding, significantly diminishing their quality of life [11]. Moreover, alterations in scar structure may allow retrograde flow of menstrual blood into the uterine cavity, thereby creating a predisposition to endometrial inflammatory conditions [12].

Uterine closure methods are also assessed in terms of their impact on long-term reproductive outcomes. Recent studies suggest that an isthmocele raises the risk of pregnancy loss and may correlate with an elevated incidence of first-trimester miscarriages [13]. One randomized controlled trial demonstrated that women with a pronounced isthmocele had a 1.5–2-fold higher risk of spontaneous miscarriage compared to patients with an intact uterine scar [14].

Identifying the optimal method of uterine closure post-cesarean section remains a critical challenge, requiring further clinical and experimental research. Current evidence underscores that double-layer closure—especially using an unlocked first layer and excluding the decidual layer—offers considerable benefits with respect to scar healing and women’s reproductive prospects [15]. However, in certain cases, single-layer closure remains an acceptable alternative, particularly if performed according to modern guidelines and techniques that minimize the risk of scar defects [16].

Despite substantial research, there is still no unified standard for selecting the uterine closure method that factors in each patient’s individual circumstances, obstetric history, and potential reproductive plans. Consequently, additional studies focusing on the long-term outcomes of different closure methods are a priority in contemporary obstetric surgery [17].

Materials and Methods

This study was designed as a retrospective cohort investigation aimed at analyzing the factors influencing the choice of uterine closure method following cesarean section. A total of 496 women who underwent cesarean delivery in maternity hospitals in Samarkand between 2019 and 2024 were included.

Inclusion criteria: women aged 18–42 years; a history of cesarean delivery for various indications; availability of medical documentation specifying the uterine closure method; planning of subsequent pregnancies or documented reproductive outcomes following cesarean delivery.

Exclusion criteria: women with severe somatic conditions affecting tissue healing (e.g., diabetes mellitus, autoimmune disorders); a history of reconstructive uterine surgeries; inflammatory diseases of the uterus and adnexa in the preceding six months before the cesarean section; a complicated postoperative course (endometritis, wound infection, septic complications).

Based on the uterine closure technique, the patients were divided into two groups:

- **Group 1 (n = 240):** women who underwent a modified uterine closure method.
- **Group 2 (n = 256):** women who received a traditional uterine closure method.

The following parameters were analyzed:

- Obstetric and gynecological history (number of deliveries, preterm deliveries, number of cesarean sections).
- Method of uterine closure (single-layer or double-layer, use of continuous or interrupted sutures).
- Myometrial thickness at the scar site, as determined by ultrasound at 6 and 12 months postoperatively.
- Frequency of isthmocele formation (identified via transvaginal sonography).
- Duration of the intergenetic interval (time from the cesarean section to the next pregnancy).
- Frequency of reproductive losses (spontaneous miscarriages, non-developing pregnancies).

- Frequency of gynecological diseases (inflammatory conditions of the uterus and adnexa, endometriosis, endometrial hyperplasia).

Methods of Investigation

1. **Clinical Methods:** collection of patients' medical histories, assessment of postoperative course (hospital stay duration, need for antibiotic therapy, incidence of complications).

2. **Instrumental Methods:** transvaginal sonography (TVS) to measure myometrial thickness at the scar site at 6 and 12 months post-surgery, and hydrosonography to detect isthmocele and evaluate its dimensions.

3. **Statistical Analysis:** conducted using SPSS version 26.0. Quantitative data were compared with the Student's t-test, while frequencies were compared using the Pearson chi-square test. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

A clinical and anamnestic analysis was performed for 496 women who underwent cesarean section. According to the chosen uterine closure technique, patients were divided into two groups: the first group included 240 (48%) women who received a modified closure, and the second group included 256 (52%) women who underwent a traditional closure. The mean age of the study participants was 29.4 ± 4.8 years, with no significant differences observed between the groups ($p > 0.05$).

An evaluation of the primary indications for cesarean delivery showed that the most common reasons were abnormalities of labor (21.1% in the modified-closure group versus 27.0% in the traditional-closure group), premature detachment of a normally situated placenta (3.5% vs. 5.5%), acute fetal hypoxia (22.8% vs. 19.9%), severe preeclampsia (7.0% vs. 4.7%), clinically narrow pelvis (19.3% vs. 14.1%), breech presentation (19.3% vs. 15.6%), and prolonged pregnancy with ineffective labor induction (7.0% vs. 13.0%). These differences did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$), indicating similar indications for cesarean section in both groups (Table 1).

Table 1.

Indications for the first cesarean section in women by uterine closure method

Groups	N	Labor Abnormalities (%)	Placental Abruption (%)	Acute Fetal Hypoxia (%)	Severe Preeclampsia (%)	Clinically Narrow Pelvis (%)	Breech Presentation (%)	Prolonged Pregnancy (%)
Modified Closure	240	21.1	3.5	22.8	7.0	19.3	19.3	7.0
Traditional Closure	256	27.0	5.5	19.9	4.7	14.1	15.6	13.0

One of the key metrics for evaluating uterine closure techniques is the thickness of the myometrium at the scar site, as measured by transvaginal ultrasound at 6 and 12 months post-surgery. In the modified-closure group, the mean myometrial thickness at 6 months was 5.9 ± 1.2 mm, increasing to 6.1 ± 1.3 mm at 12 months. In contrast,

the corresponding values in the traditional-closure group were 4.8 ± 1.4 mm and 5.0 ± 1.2 mm, respectively. These differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting better scar healing with the modified closure method (Table 2).

Table 2.

Myometrial thickness at the scar site at 6 and 12 months after cesarean section

Groups	N	Myometrial Thickness at 6 Months (mm)	Myometrial Thickness at 12 Months (mm)
Modified Closure	240	5.9 ± 1.2	6.1 ± 1.3
Traditional Closure	256	4.8 ± 1.4	5.0 ± 1.2

The formation of an isthmocele (a defect in the uterine scar) was observed in 14.0% of cases in the first group and in 21.5% of patients in the second group. The mean size of the isthmocele was 3.2 ± 1.1 mm in the first group compared to 4.5 ± 1.3 mm in the second ($p < 0.05$), further supporting the benefits of the modified closure in reducing the risk of scar dehiscence.

The intergenetic interval (time from a cesarean section to the next pregnancy) was significantly longer in the modified-closure group: an

interval of less than 18 months was recorded for 12.3% of women (versus 16.8% in the traditional-closure group), 18–24 months for 82.5% (versus 67.2%), and more than 24 months for 5.3% (versus 16.0%) ($p < 0.05$). These data indicate that with modified closure, myometrial recovery is faster, allowing women to plan subsequent pregnancies at more optimal intervals (Table 3).

Table 3.

Duration of the intergenetic interval in women after cesarean section

Groups	N	<18 Months (%)	18–24 Months (%)	>24 Months (%)
Modified Closure	240	12.3	82.5	5.3
Traditional Closure	256	16.8	67.2	16.0

Overall, these findings indicate that the uterine closure technique has a major impact on scar healing, the formation of isthmocele, the frequency of reproductive losses, and the duration of the intergenetic interval. Adopting a modified closure method improves myometrial thickness, lowers the likelihood of scar dehiscence, and optimizes future reproductive outcomes in women post-cesarean. Despite the observed advantages, further research is needed to more comprehensively assess the influence of various uterine closure techniques on long-term reproductive and gynecological outcomes.

Discussion of the Results

Analysis of the collected data confirmed that the choice of uterine closure technique substantially affects postoperative scar quality, the incidence of isthmocele, reproductive outcomes, and the intergenetic interval. Our findings are consistent with the literature, which suggests that optimizing surgical techniques in cesarean sections can reduce complications and improve women's reproductive health [1, 2].

According to our data, the use of a modified uterine closure method resulted in more pronounced restoration of myometrial thickness, as evidenced by significant differences in transvaginal ultrasound parameters between the groups. At 6 months postpartum, the mean

myometrial thickness in the modified-closure group was 5.9 ± 1.2 mm, while in the traditional-closure group it was 4.8 ± 1.4 mm ($p < 0.05$). After 12 months, a similar pattern persisted, indicating better outcomes with the modified closure (6.1 ± 1.3 mm vs. 5.0 ± 1.2 mm; $p < 0.05$). These findings align with other studies reporting that insufficient myometrial thickness increases the risk of uterine scar dehiscence and possible uterine rupture in future pregnancies [3, 4].

The frequency of isthmocele formation, one of the most significant long-term complications of cesarean section, was also higher in the traditional-closure group (21.5% vs. 14.0%, $p < 0.05$). Literature indicates that isthmocele can be associated with specific closure techniques, particularly single-layer continuous sutures, which raise the risk of defect formation [5, 6]. Given that isthmocele is associated with dyspareunia, chronic pelvic pain, menstrual irregularities, and infertility, selecting an optimal surgical approach is critical [7].

The intergenetic interval was also longer in the modified-closure group, reflecting a more stable uterine scar and enabling safer planning of subsequent pregnancies. An interval of less than 18 months was noted in 12.3% of women (vs. 16.8% in the traditional group), while the interval of 18–24 months was reported in 82.5% (vs. 67.2%, $p < 0.05$). These data support the hypothesis that refining closure techniques can

accelerate the functional recovery of the myometrium, which is particularly relevant for women aiming to conceive again [8].

Regarding reproductive losses, the incidence of spontaneous miscarriages in patients who received the modified closure was lower (17.5% vs. 21.5%, $p < 0.05$), and the rate of non-developing pregnancies was 10.5% vs. 18.0%. This underscores the pivotal role of uterine scar integrity in successful pregnancy outcomes, consistent with other authors' conclusions [9, 10].

Gynecological morbidity in women with a uterine scar who underwent different closure methods did not differ significantly; however, there was a tendency toward a reduced frequency of inflammatory diseases (36.8% vs. 44.5%), endometrial hyperplasia (5.3% vs. 8.8%), and secondary infertility (8.8% vs. 14.5%) in the modified-closure group. Although these differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), they may suggest potential long-term benefits of more advanced surgical techniques [11].

Overall, the findings indicate that employing a modified uterine closure method after cesarean section enhances scar integrity, lowers the incidence of isthmocele, reduces the risk of reproductive losses, and optimizes the intergenetic interval. Further research is warranted to explore and refine closure techniques that can yield the most favorable reproductive outcomes for women who undergo cesarean delivery.

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ЖУРНАЛ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ И УРО-НЕФРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,

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